

QUIZ

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FIRST NAME: Feng

PROGRAM CODE: MIPH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied U.S. U.K. conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following is NOT required for a good academic essay?

- An academic essay should persuade readers of an idea or argument based on evidence.
- An academic essay should have supporting information, including hearsay evidence.¹**
- An academic essay should have a thesis answer to the question.
- An academic essay should answer a question or task.

2. Which of the following is NOT considered plagiarism?

- Unacknowledged citations in a submitted response paper.
- Copying words from an internet webpage without appropriate attribution.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 1.

- Paraphrasing someone else's ideas, and then citing the source of ideas.**²
- Having someone write a paper for you.
3. **Which of the following Latin expression means *for instance*?**
- et alii*.
- in situ*.
- exempli gratia*.³
- id est*.
4. **These different kinds of thinking are often divided into six levels. Which of the following is the most advanced level?**
- Analyzing.
- Understanding.
- Synthesizing.
- Evaluating.**⁴
5. **Which of the following journal citations in a reference list is correct according to the author-date style in the Turabian manual?**

² Ibid., 5-10.

³ Ibid., 56-58.

⁴ Patrick Sebranek, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer, *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*, 4th ed. (Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999), 283.

- Kiser, L. J. (2011). *Silencing the Lambs: Economics, Ethics, and Animal Life in Medieval Franciscan Hagiography*. *Modern Philology* 108, no. 3: 323–42. Accessed September 18, 2011. [http://dx .doi .org /10.1086/658052](http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/658052).
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 - Kiser, Lisa J. 2011. “Silencing the Lambs: Economics, Ethics, and Animal Life in Medieval Franciscan Hagiography.” *Modern Philology* 108, no. 3 (February): 323–42. Accessed September 18, 2011. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1086/658052>.⁵**
6. **Per the Turabian manual,⁶ what are the two common scholarly citation styles? Please select the most accurate styles of citation forms.**
- Parenthetical style
 - Reference style
 - Notes-bibliography style**
 - Author-date style**

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne C. Booth et al., 8th edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 130.

⁶ *Ibid.*, 87.

7. For researchers, they may use different levels of sources, which of the following level of source is NOT mentioned in the Turabian manual?⁷

- Quaternary Sources
- Secondary Sources
- Primary Sources
- Tertiary Sources

8. Which of the following normally will NOT be considered as raw data when reporting research results?

- Lists of observations.
- A graph of data in a published journal.⁸
- Values documented on a laboratory notebook.
- Medical chart records in a clinic.

9. Which of the following abbreviations or contractions is accepted in the style guide by the University of Oxford?

- A.M.
- Dr.
- DPhil⁹

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 24.

⁸ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 10-11.

⁹ *Ibid.*, 75.

Ph.D.

10. **The format for presenting items in a reference list in World Health Organization publications is based on which of the following writing styles?**

The Vancouver Style.¹⁰

The Chicago Style

The American Psychological Association (APA) Style

the American Medical Association (AMA) Style

¹⁰ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide*. 2nd ed. (Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004), 25.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.
- Sebranek, Patrick, Dave Kemper, and Verne Meyer. *Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning*. 4th ed. Wilmington, MA: Great Source Education Group, 1999.
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- World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.